

Genetics

Inheritance studies for aroma in two aromatic varieties of Pakistan

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Basmati 370 and Basmati 198 are highly aromatic, long-grain indica types. Rice pests have caused severe yield losses during the past few years.

Rice breeders would like to develop cultivars with excellent cooking quality, strong aroma, and resistance to major pests. The inheritance pattern of aroma is being studied systematically to achieve this goal.

We crossed parents Basmati 370 and Basmati 198 with Tetep, a nonaromatic short-grain variety with resistance to many rice insect pests and diseases, during 1990 kharif (monsoon). F_1 and parent seeds were sown during 1991 kharif. F_1 plants were selfed and backcrossed to the aromatic parents to produce BC_1 and F_2 . The aromatic varieties were again crossed with Tetep to produce F_1 seed.

We grew 25 plants each for P_1 , P_2 , P_3 , and F_1 (single 6.3-m row), 100 plants for BC_1 (4 rows), and 200 plants for F_2 (8 rows) in 1992 kharif. A plant-to-plant and row-to-row distance of 23 cm was used.

We evaluated aroma 45 d after transplanting. Two-gram leaf blades from single plants were cut into small pieces, put into test tubes, and soaked in 10 ml of 1.7% KOH solution for 10 min at 25-30 °C. Samples were classified as aromatic or nonaromatic by smelling.

All F_1 plants were nonaromatic, indicating that aroma in the parents was recessive (see table). Segregating ratio of nonaromatic to aromatic plants was 1:1 in BC_1 and 3:1 in F_2 , further confirming the monogenic inheritance of aroma. Fixation of aroma in early-segregating generations is expected. ■

Behavior of parents, F_1 , BC_1 , and F_2 with regard to aroma 45 d after transplanting.

Designation	Plants (no.)			Ratio of nonaromatic to aromatic		χ^2	P
	Tested	Non-aromatic	Aromatic	Actual	Expected		
Parents							
Basmati 370	25	0	25	0:1	0:1		
Basmati 198	25	0	25	0:1	0:1		
Tetep	25	0	0	1:0	1:0		
F_1							
Basmati 370/Tetep	25	25	0	1:0	1:0		
Basmati 198/Tetep	25	25	0	1:0	1:0		
BC_1							
Basmati 370//Basmati 370/Tetep	100	53	47	1:1.1	1:1	0.36	0.50-0.75
Basmati 198//Basmati 198/Tetep	100	52	48	1:1.1	1:1	0.16	0.50-0.75
Total	200	105	95	1:1.1	1:1	0.50	0.25-0.50
F_2							
Basmati 370/Tetep	200	148	52	2.9:1	3:1	0.11	0.50-0.75
Basmati 198/Tetep	200	153	47	3.7:1	3:1	0.24	0.50-0.75
Total	400	301	99	3:1	3:1	0.01	> 0.90

Sensitivity to gibberellic acid (GA_3) of seedlings and endosperms of rice lines with different genes for height

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Five lines carrying different height genes were studied: Mutant T (tall gene Sd_1) and Mutant D (semidwarf gene sd_1), both derived from a heterozygous tall mutant of the cross B_3 /Xin-You-Zhan); Tall Zhen-Shan (recessive tall gene eui) derived from the eui stock; Chao-Ai (recessive dwarf gene $sds_{(w)}$) derived from Xue-He-Ai-Zhao; and dominant dwarf D_{53} . We measured plant elongation 12 d after spraying with 20 ppm GA_3 . Meanwhile, endosperms of the lines were

plated in media with 0.5% soluble starch and 10 ppm GA_3 ; they were stained with I_2 -KI 72 h after culture.

Seedling responses to GA_3 were different among the lines (see table). Based on elongation ratio, Mutant D, Tall Zhen-Shan, and D_{53} were more sensitive to GA_3 than were Mutant T and Chao-Ai. Sensitiveness of the genes for height to GA_3 were $eui > D_{53} > sd_1 > Sd_1 > sds_{(w)}$.

GA_3 induced the endosperms to produce α -amylase, which degraded the starch in the medium. When stained with I_2 -KI, the resulting white spots were larger around the endosperms of Mutant D, Tall Zhen-Shan, and D_{53} , all of which produced more α -amylase than around those of Mutant T and Chao-Ai, which produced less of the enzyme (see figure). Results indicate that genotypes sensitive

Elongation ratios of seedlings treated with GA_3 .

Line	Genotype	Seedling height (cm)		Elongation ratio (%)
		0 ppm GA_3	20 ppm GA_3	
Mutant T	$Sd_1 Sd_1$	19.9	24.6	23.6
Mutant D	$sd_1 sd_1$	14.7	26.0	76.9
Tall Zhen-Shan	$eui eui$	14.5	28.5	96.6
D_{53}	$D_{53} D_{53}$	10.1	18.5	83.2
Chao-Ai	$sds_{(w)} sds_{(w)}$	9.0	10.4	15.6